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2 Main Manuscript for

3 Declining coral calcification to enhance twenty-first century ocean 4 carbon uptake by gigatonnes

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1 **Abstract**

2 The sensitivity of coral reefs to climate change is well-established. As the ocean's warm and acidify,
3 the calcification of coral reefs declines with net calcium carbonate dissolution projected under even
4 moderate emissions trajectories. The impact of this on the global carbon cycle is however yet to be
5 accounted for. Here we use a synthesis of the sensitivity of coral reef calcification to climate change,
6 alongside reef distribution products to estimate alkalinity and dissolved inorganic carbon fluxes
7 resulting from reductions in reef calcification. Using a global ocean biogeochemical model, we
8 simulate the impact on ocean carbon uptake under different emissions scenarios, accounting for
9 uncertainty in present-day calcification rates. Reductions in net coral reef carbonate production can
10 enhance the ocean carbon sink by up to 1.25 GtCO₂ yr⁻¹ by mid-century (0.48 GtCO₂ yr⁻¹ median
11 estimate) with cumulative ocean carbon uptake up to 13 % greater by 2300 (7 % median estimate).
12 Our findings indicate that accounting for the coral reef feedback in projections will increase
13 estimates of the remaining carbon budget associated with global warming thresholds, as well as
14 the likelihood that net zero emissions can be achieved without negative emissions.

15 **Significance Statement**

16 Climate change is anticipated to suppress coral reef calcification with net dissolution expected
17 under even moderate emissions scenarios. The impact of this on the global carbon cycle is however
18 unknown as these ecosystems are not represented in Earth system models. Using a global
19 biogeochemical model, we estimate that the coral reef climate feedback will enhance ocean carbon
20 uptake by up to 13% by the year 2300. This negative feedback increases estimates of the remaining
21 carbon budget associated with global warming thresholds such as the Paris Agreement goal of
22 limiting the global increase in temperature to 2°C above preindustrial levels.
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24

25 **Main Text**

26 The oceans currently absorb around 25 % of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions (1, 2), limiting the
27 fraction that remains in the atmosphere and the resulting climate change. Future ocean carbon
28 uptake is therefore a key determinant of the remaining carbon budgets associated with global
29 warming targets. The solubility pump is the principal driver of projected ocean carbon uptake (1)
30 and is mainly driven by the CO₂ partial pressure (*p*CO₂) gradient between the atmosphere and
31 surface ocean. While the projected change in the air-sea *p*CO₂ gradient, and therefore future ocean
32 carbon uptake, is dominated by anthropogenic emissions of CO₂ (3–5), perturbations to ocean
33 biogeochemical processes (6–8) and model uncertainty (2, 4) can also affect uptake.

34 Coral reef ecosystems have long been known to modify local seawater chemistry and in turn air-
35 sea CO₂ fluxes (9–11). The dominant processes responsible for such changes are net ecosystem
36 production (gross primary production minus respiration; NEP) and net ecosystem calcification
37 (gross calcification minus CaCO₃ dissolution; NEC). Positive net production reduces dissolved
38 inorganic carbon (DIC) concentrations, decreasing seawater *p*CO₂. Positive net calcification
39 however, reduces total alkalinity (Alk) and dissolved inorganic carbon, in a ratio of 2:1, increasing
40 the *p*CO₂ of seawater. The balance of organic-to-inorganic carbon production is therefore the
41 principal driver of whether a reef acts as a net source or sink of atmospheric CO₂. This balance can
42 be influenced by multiple factors including community composition (12, 13), nutrient supply (14),
43 disease (15) and grazing pressure (16). Historically however, studies have shown that the relatively
44 low organic production and high calcification of coral reefs produces a net source of CO₂ to the
45 atmosphere (17–19).

46 Alongside other stressors, ocean warming and acidification act to reduce the net ecosystem
47 calcification of coral reefs through processes such as bleaching (20–22), reduced calcification (23,
48 24) and enhanced sediment dissolution (25). Observations suggest that global net calcification is
49 already regionally declining (23, 26, 27), with models projecting a mid-century transition to a state
50 of net CaCO₃ dissolution (negative NEC) under even moderate emissions scenarios (25, 28–30).

51 Other factors being equal, this decline will increase ocean alkalinity and DIC in a 2:1 molar ratio
52 that acts to reduce the $p\text{CO}_2$ of seawater and enhance ocean carbon uptake from the atmosphere.
53 It therefore represents a negative climate feedback currently unresolved by Earth system models
54 (31) and may contribute to biases in projected ocean carbon uptake.

55 **Simulating declining coral reef calcification**

56 We simulate the biogeochemical impact of declining coral reef net calcification as an anomalous
57 source of alkalinity and DIC in ocean regions containing reefs. The magnitude of these fluxes is
58 dependent on both the assumed historical rate of global coral reef calcification and the decline
59 under different future emissions scenarios (Fig. 1). We derived 9 time-evolving estimates of future
60 alkalinity and DIC fluxes, based on three historical values of global coral reef calcification (30, 150
61 and 300 TgC yr^{-1}) thought to encompass observational uncertainty (32), and exponential decay
62 functions of calcification under different emissions scenarios (Representative Concentration
63 Pathways 2.6 (RCP2.6), 4.5 (RCP4.5), and 8.5 (RCP8.5) (33). Our central historical calcification
64 estimate of 150 TgC yr^{-1} is consistent with previously published best estimates and a likely range
65 of 30-300 TgC yr^{-1} (32, 34). The functions of declining net calcification are based on a meta-analysis
66 of experimental, mesocosm and in situ estimates of coral reef calcification under each RCP, and
67 include both living and non-living components of the reef carbonate budget (e.g. coral and crustose
68 coralline algae calcification, sediment dissolution and bioerosion) (28). The anomalies in carbonate
69 production are estimated to year 2300 assuming an inexhaustible CaCO_3 reservoir. Given the
70 current reef CaCO_3 reservoir has typically arisen over the last 5000-10,000 years and maximal net
71 dissolution rates are less than historical calcification rates, this assumption is supported on multi-
72 centennial timescales.

73 The impact of the coral reef derived fluxes of alkalinity and DIC on ocean anthropogenic carbon
74 uptake (C_{ant}) was simulated using the PISCES global ocean biogeochemical model (35). PISCES
75 simulates the cycles of organic and inorganic ocean carbon, total alkalinity, oxygen, and essential
76 marine nutrients (N, P, Si, and Fe). It includes two phytoplankton functional types and two
77 zooplankton size classes, alongside two particulate organic matter size classes, particulate
78 inorganic matter (calcite) and dissolved organic matter. Pelagic calcification is implicitly
79 parameterized as a function of organic matter production and consistent with current generation
80 ocean biogeochemical models. However sediment dissolution and benthic calcification, including
81 that of coral reefs, are unresolved (31). Air–sea CO_2 fluxes, follow Ocean Model Intercomparison
82 Project protocols (36), with gas exchange dependent on the air–sea partial pressure gradient and
83 a parameterization of the instantaneous gas transfer velocity that depends on 10 m atmospheric
84 wind speed (37, 38).

85 This PISCES version utilised is similar to that described in Aumont et al. (2015) (35), and used in
86 multiple Earth system models (e.g. IPSL-CM6A-LR) (39), however the burial fraction of plankton-
87 derived particulate inorganic carbon (PIC) was adjusted so that the global alkalinity inventory is
88 conserved at preindustrial levels without the need of a restoring scheme (40) and the
89 parameterization of diazotrophy was modified (41). The model was forced with physical ocean
90 outputs derived from the IPSL-CM5A-LR Earth system model and concentrations of greenhouse
91 gases consistent with the RCPs (33). Coral reef derived fluxes of alkalinity and DIC were simulated
92 as boundary conditions in the surface ocean of regions where reefs have been identified (42), in a
93 molar ratio of 2:1 consistent with a decline in net carbonate production. These fluxes are provided
94 continuously and neglect sub-annual and regional diversity in the rate of decline.

95 **Ocean carbon sink enhancement**

96 Our historical simulations of ocean anthropogenic carbon uptake are broadly consistent with the
97 magnitude and spatial distribution of observational estimates (Fig. 2, Fig. S1). In future scenarios,
98 the principal driver of divergence in projected anthropogenic carbon uptake by the ocean is the
99 atmospheric CO_2 concentration associated with each RCP (Fig. 2). In the absence of coral reefs,

100 the C_{ant} flux peaks at 3.0, 3.7 and 6.1 PgC yr⁻¹ in RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, respectively. This
101 is consistent with ESM simulations performed as part of the CMIP exercises (4, 5). The coral reef
102 carbonate feedback can however substantially enhance projected C_{ant} uptake.

103 Coral-driven increases in the ocean carbon sink reach near-maximal values in the mid 21st century,
104 with sink enhancement maintained on multi-centennial timescales. Under the median estimate of
105 historical reef carbonate production combined with the moderate emissions scenario (RCP4.5₁₅₀),
106 C_{ant} uptake is enhanced by 0.13 PgC yr⁻¹ by 2050, increasing to 0.17 PgC yr⁻¹ in 2100 and persisting
107 at this level until 2300 (Fig. 2). The range in peak C_{ant} uptake enhancement across the simulation
108 ensemble ranges from 0.02 PgC yr⁻¹ (RCP2.6₃₀ in year 2211) to 0.44 PgC yr⁻¹ (RCP8.5₃₀₀ in year
109 2163). In the median scenario (RCP4.5₁₅₀), the cumulative ocean carbon sink is enhanced by 11
110 PgC by 2100 (3%), with this increasing to 46 PgC by 2300 (7%) and by up to 110 PgC (8%) in 2300
111 under RCP8.5₃₀₀. Given that the end-of-century range in ESM estimates of ocean carbon uptake
112 is between ~0.2 PgC yr⁻¹ (for the highest mitigation scenarios) and ~0.8 PgC yr⁻¹ (for highest
113 emission scenarios) (4), coral reef induced enhancement of the ocean carbon sink represents a
114 relatively substantial potential contributor to model uncertainty that is currently unaccounted for.

115 Uncertainty in the coral reef induced enhancement of ocean C_{ant} uptake is primarily a consequence
116 of the assumed historical carbonate production rate and, to a lesser extent, scenario uncertainty
117 (RCP). The C_{ant} uptake enhancement is similar between RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 simulations for a
118 given historical carbonate production rate, indicative of maximum carbonate production declines
119 being reached under moderate emissions scenarios (see methods). This also reflects the
120 characterization of coral reef ecosystems as potential tipping elements in the Earth system that are
121 susceptible to abrupt change even at current warming levels (43). Refining estimates of both
122 historical coral reef carbonate production as well as its sensitivity to climate change is therefore
123 critical to constraining estimates of the enhancement of ocean carbon uptake.

124 The simulated increase in ocean anthropogenic carbon uptake is locally highest in the regions of
125 coral reefs such as the coral triangle. However enhanced uptake outside coral regions is
126 responsible for 50 to 80 % of the global enhancement (Fig. S2). This is indicative of the seawater
127 residence time in reef regions being less than the air-sea equilibration time of induced $p\text{CO}_2$
128 anomalies and has been similarly demonstrated in simulations of afforestation and alkalinity
129 enhancement (44).

130 The fraction of enhancement that occurs in reef regions is almost entirely determined by the
131 atmospheric CO_2 concentration (i.e. RCP) and not the historical global carbonate production rate
132 (Fig. S2). This is indicative of the balance between seawater residence time and air-sea
133 equilibration time exhibiting limited change for different reef net calcification anomalies in our
134 simulations. While most of the ocean carbon uptake enhancement is located in reef regions when
135 reef calcification initially decreases (Fig. S2), the fraction occurring in coral regions then declines
136 across the three RCPs to around 25% in 2040. This reflects increasing advection of unequilibrated
137 water masses out of coral regions and limited differences between scenarios up to this point. In
138 RCP2.6, the fraction further declines to around 18% in 2300 while in RCP4.5 the decline is more
139 gradual to around 23% in 2300. Counterintuitively, under RCP8.5 the fraction increases around
140 2070 to ~50% of the global enhancement in 2300. This is likely due to the reduction in CO_2
141 equilibration time in this very high CO_2 scenario (45) alongside increases in surface seawater
142 residence time.

143 **Carbon budget consequences**

144 Our simulations indicate that the coral reef feedback could increase 21st century ocean carbon
145 uptake by up to 5%. This effect is smaller than that of the soft tissue pump, which enhances ocean
146 carbon uptake by 5–17% in moderate-to-high emissions scenarios, according to current ESMs (46).
147 Notably, the soft tissue pump achieves this increase despite a global decline in organic carbon
148 export. Instead, the enhancement results from longer residence times of respired DIC due to

149 increased stratification and a slowdown in ocean overturning. In the absence of circulation changes,
150 pelagic carbonate pump changes have been estimated to increase 21st century ocean carbon
151 uptake by up to 5% in ESMs however this is highly uncertain with reductions in carbon uptake also
152 simulated (40).

153 The identified coral reef feedback, currently unresolved in ESMs, increases remaining carbon
154 budgets associated with given temperature thresholds and therefore has policy consequences. The
155 latest IPCC assessment report provides an upper estimate and likelihood associated with currently
156 unresolved Earth system feedbacks (e.g. permafrost melt) (1). Based on our simulations the coral
157 reef feedback has a potential 21st century magnitude comparable to boreal forest dieback (although
158 opposite in sign). This is substantially larger than other potential feedbacks due to unresolved
159 marine ecology in ESMs. For example, the impact of climate change on planktonic ecosystem
160 structure and elemental stoichiometry is estimated to decrease ocean carbon uptake by < 1% (8),
161 while climate-driven proliferation of gelatinous zooplankton has been shown to enhance ocean
162 carbon uptake by < 0.1 % (47). Moreover, contrary to most documented unresolved Earth system
163 feedbacks, the likelihood of the coral reef feedback occurring this century is very high. Indeed,
164 multiple lines of evidence indicate it is probably already occurring (23, 27).

165 Scenarios consistent with the Paris Agreement goal of limiting the global increase in temperature
166 to 2°C above preindustrial levels have associated cumulative negative emissions of 330 GtCO₂
167 (260-440 GtCO₂ interquartile range) (48). However cumulative ocean carbon uptake over the 21st
168 century may be underestimated by up to 11 GtCO₂ in high-mitigation scenarios consistent with this
169 goal due to the coral reef feedback (RCP2.6₃₀₀), with a corresponding decrease in required negative
170 emissions.

171 The global surface air temperature change associated with net zero emissions, also known as the
172 zero emissions commitment (ZEC), is estimated between -0.36 and 0.29°C after 50 years of
173 ceased emissions (49). This range reflects uncertainty in whether the stabilisation of global
174 temperatures is consistent with limited residual emissions or will indeed require sustained negative
175 emissions. Ocean carbon uptake post zero emissions is a critical determinant of the ZEC, with
176 greater uptake offsetting declines in ocean heat uptake and therefore typically associated with a
177 lower ZEC (49). Estimates of ZEC however, are derived from models that fail to account for the
178 coral reef feedback. Its inclusion would enhance ocean carbon uptake post zero emissions,
179 reducing the ZEC and therefore increasing the likelihood that stabilising global temperature can be
180 achieved without negative emissions.

181 **Coral reef organic production and other assumptions**

182 In contrast to net calcification, coral reef organic net ecosystem production is assumed constant in
183 our simulations. This has the potential to influence the magnitude of the simulated coral reef
184 feedback. A general increase in coral reef organic production coincident with calcification declines
185 over the last 50 years has been documented (50). Such increases would typically act to increase
186 the projected coral reef-induced enhancement of the ocean carbon sink. Nonetheless, local studies
187 have documented declines in net organic production post bleaching and suggested such trends
188 may continue under future warming (51–53). This would likely act to attenuate the projected
189 enhancement of the ocean carbon sink. Some reefs have even been shown to be in a current state
190 of both net carbonate dissolution and net respiration, with each metabolic cycle highly seasonally
191 variable and future changes undetermined (54). In short, the response of coral reef organic
192 production to climate change is highly uncertain, likely to be spatially variable and could act to both
193 increase and attenuate the projected enhancement of the ocean carbon sink. We currently lack the
194 observational and experimental constraints required to simulate transient changes in reef organic
195 production but, when possible, this should be incorporated into projections to refine estimates of
196 the coral reef feedback.

197 Our simulations assume no spatial heterogeneity in reef-derived inputs of alkalinity and DIC in
198 response to carbonate production declines. This is inconsistent with observations which show
199 spatial variability in both present-day coral net carbonate production rates and estimated declines
200 in response to climate change (28, 50, 55). Many Caribbean reefs are already at accretionary stasis
201 or net dissolving (54, 55) while Pacific reefs generally exhibit higher present-day carbonate
202 production and are considered more likely to sustain positive net carbonate production in the future
203 (28). Incorporating such heterogeneity into projections may therefore affect regional carbon uptake
204 enhancement. However given that the sensitivity of ocean carbon uptake to alkalinity increases
205 exhibits limited spatial variability across the tropics (56), the impact on global ocean carbon uptake
206 is likely to be minimal. Within this context, it should be noted that the impact of other stressors such
207 as fishing pressure, increased disease prevalence, cyclone intensity and nutrification (29, 57, 58)
208 is currently unaccounted for in global estimates of future coral carbonate production (28, 59).
209 Incorporating these stressors into projections is likely to enhance projected declines in calcification,
210 increase ocean carbon sink enhancement and introduce additional spatiotemporal variability.

211 A further limitation of our simulations is that atmospheric CO₂ concentrations are prescribed and
212 therefore unaffected by the enhanced air–sea carbon fluxes attributable to reductions in coral reef
213 carbonate production. In an emissions-driven model, enhanced ocean carbon uptake would act to
214 decrease atmospheric CO₂ concentrations, typically reducing terrestrial carbon uptake and
215 resulting in lesser overall enhancement of the ocean carbon sink (60). Assessing the magnitude of
216 the coral reef carbonate pump feedback in simulations that account for atmospheric and terrestrial
217 carbon cycle feedbacks is therefore required. The recent development of an Earth system model
218 of intermediate complexity coral reef module (61), which might be adapted for implementation
219 within ESMs, represents progress in this direction.

220 **Measuring the feedback in the real world**

221 Confirmation of the coral reef feedback with measurements is clearly desirable. Coral reef alkalinity
222 measurements are perhaps most promising in this regard as they are both conservative with
223 respect to temperature variations and unaffected by air-sea gas exchange. However, the maximum
224 simulated change in surface ocean alkalinity induced by carbonate production declines is
225 approximately 50 mmol m⁻³ century⁻¹ in Indian Ocean regions of RCP8.5₃₀₀ (Fig. S3). In our median
226 scenario (RCP4.5₁₅₀) the simulated surface ocean alkalinity trend is reduced by half, with most
227 coral reef regions exhibiting increases of 10-20 mmol m⁻³ century⁻¹. Although trends in alkalinity
228 would be higher at the spatial scales of an actual reef, the extremely high natural variability of
229 alkalinity in reef environments (62) (Fig. S3) suggests that multi-decadal to multi-centennial time
230 series are required for the impact of declining reef calcification on seawater carbonate chemistry to
231 emerge from natural variability. For this reason, the best estimates of the future coral reef climate
232 feedback may depend on alternative, more indirect estimates of changing reef carbonate budgets
233 (e.g. 31, 32).

234

235 **Materials and Methods**

236 **Model and simulations**

237 As the biogeochemical models developed for ESMs lack a representation of coral reefs (31), we
238 impose the flux of alkalinity and DIC that results from decreasing coral reef carbonate production
239 as a time dependent model boundary condition. This perturbation approach is possible because a
240 given decline in net ecosystem calcification has an identical impact on seawater alkalinity and DIC
241 regardless of whether net ecosystem calcification remains positive or transitions to a negative state
242 (i.e. net dissolution). The addition of alkalinity and DIC in coral reef regions is based on published
243 central estimates of present-day reef carbonate production, and production declines under RCP2.6,
244 RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 (28). The central estimate of present-day coral reef carbonate production is
245 $2.8 \text{ kgCaCO}_3 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. This has been projected to decrease to 0.95, -0.63 and -1.45 $\text{kgCaCO}_3 \text{ m}^{-2}$
246 yr^{-1} in 2050 and thereafter to 0.73, -1.39 and -1.57 $\text{kgCaCO}_3 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in 2100 under RCP2.6, RCP4.5
247 and RCP8.5, respectively due to warming and acidification (28). These projections do not account
248 for other stressors such as fishing pressure, greater disease exposure and nutrification which would
249 likely exacerbate declines (27, 29, 57, 58). We do not account for the uncertain potential of symbiont
250 adaptive capacity to influence projections of future coral reef carbonate production (59). Under low
251 emissions scenarios, such adaptive capacity may result in less severe production declines, while
252 under medium and high emissions, the transition to net dissolution could be delayed. Although the
253 RCPs have been updated to SSPs (Shared Socioeconomic Pathways) in the latest coupled model
254 intercomparison project (63), each of the RCPs used here has an SSP analogue that exhibits
255 similar albeit greater surface ocean warming and acidification for a comparable radiative forcing
256 (64).

257 By fitting exponential decay functions to these estimates, relative anomalies in future reef carbonate
258 production can be estimated annually. However, to convert these into fluxes of alkalinity and DIC
259 the historical (pre-2005) global carbonate production of coral reefs is required. We adopt a central
260 estimate of historical global carbonate production of 150 TgC yr^{-1} ($1.25 \text{ PgCaCO}_3 \text{ yr}^{-1}$). This is
261 consistent with previously published central estimates with a likely range of $30\text{-}300 \text{ TgC yr}^{-1}$ (32)
262 and global reef carbonate production estimates ($78\text{-}100 \text{ TgC yr}^{-1}$) based on lower historical
263 estimates of reef extent (34).

264 In order to encompass the uncertainty in historical global carbonate production we perform
265 simulations for each RCP assuming carbonate production of 30, 150 and 300 TgC yr^{-1} (0.25, 1.25
266 and $2.50 \text{ PgCaCO}_3 \text{ yr}^{-1}$). These carbonate production values are denoted as subscripts in
267 simulation names (i.e. the 9 future simulations are: RCP2.6₃₀, RCP2.6₁₅₀, RCP2.6₃₀₀, RCP4.5₃₀,
268 RCP4.5₁₅₀, RCP4.5₃₀₀, RCP8.5₃₀, RCP8.5₁₅₀, RCP8.5₃₀₀). In addition to these simulations an 1850
269 to 2005 historical simulation is performed, from which the 9 RCP simulations are extended in 2005
270 to 2300, as well as a coincident preindustrial control simulation used to remove model drift and
271 calculate anthropogenic carbon fluxes. We assume that the impact of reductions in coral reef
272 carbonate production starts to occur in 2005, coincident with the RCPs. This is inconsistent with at
273 least regional evidence that reef carbonate production may have declined prior to 2005 (23, 26, 27)
274 but we lack the data to constrain global production declines over the 1850-2005 historical
275 simulations (28). Any such decline however, would act to increase the magnitude of the simulated
276 ocean carbon uptake enhancement over the duration of our simulations.

277 In the simulation of minimal carbonate production decline (RCP2.6₃₀), reef-derived alkalinity and
278 DIC fluxes increase to 0.004 and 0.002 Pmol globally by 2100, respectively, where they are
279 maintained until 2300. While in the simulation of maximal carbonate production decline
280 (RCP8.5₃₀₀), alkalinity and DIC fluxes increase to 0.08 and 0.04 Pmol by 2100, respectively, where
281 thereafter they are maintained. Reef-derived model inputs of alkalinity and DIC are equally
282 distributed across all model grid cells documented to contain warm water coral reefs. As such, we
283 do not account for any regional disparities in the resilience of coral reef carbonate production. We
284 also do not account for the potential for carbonate production declines to reduce projected ocean

285 acidification and therefore attenuate acidification-driven declines in carbonate production.
286 However, the impact of carbonate production declines on projected ocean acidification is highly
287 limited (Fig. S4). Across all simulations most of the decline in coral reef carbonate production occurs
288 prior to 2050 with limited declines thereafter and virtually no further decline post 2150. This is
289 consistent with metanalysis studies (28) and evidence that coral reefs represent a tipping element
290 susceptible to abrupt change at current warming levels (43).

291 **Model evaluation**

292 The PISCES model utilised here is similar to that in multiple ESMs that have contributed to the
293 latest coupled model intercomparison project phase 6 (CMIP6). Our offline model configuration has
294 previously been used to assess potential evolution of the pelagic carbonate pump and the
295 simulated historical anthropogenic carbon uptake in the absence of the coral reef feedback, and is
296 consistent with data-based ocean carbon uptake estimates (2) (Fig. S1) and the CMIP6 ensemble
297 spread (40). Both the spatial distribution of simulated air-sea total carbon fluxes and recent
298 historical trends in globally integrated fluxes are consistent across model simulations and
299 observational products.

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542 **Figures**

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545 **Fig. 1. Global declines in coral reef carbonate production and the associated fluxes of**
546 **alkalinity and dissolved inorganic carbon.** The (A), estimated global coral reef net ecosystem
547 calcification (TgC yr⁻¹ and PgCaCO₃ yr⁻¹) and the (B), simulated global flux of alkalinity (Pmol yr⁻¹)
548 and DIC associated with carbonate production decline in each RCP. Black lines represent the
549 historical unperturbed rate of global carbonate production (30, 150 and 300 TgC yr⁻¹), with the same
550 line type used for corresponding RCP simulations and the assumed carbonate historical production
551 rate denoted in subscript.

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565 **Fig. 2. Enhancement of the global ocean anthropogenic carbon sink due to reductions in**
 566 **coral reef carbonate production.** The simulated (A), annual ocean anthropogenic carbon uptake
 567 (PgC yr⁻¹), (B), enhancement due to coral reef degradation (PgC yr⁻¹), (C), cumulative
 568 anthropogenic ocean carbon uptake (PgC) and (D), enhancement due to coral reef degradation
 569 (PgC). Anomalies in ocean carbon uptake due to coral reef carbonate production declines are
 570 shown relative to their respective RCP. No decline in coral reef carbonate production is simulated
 571 prior to 2005. Data-based estimates of the ocean anthropogenic carbon sink in the 2000s are
 572 shown in magenta in panel A with error bars representing 1 standard deviation (2). The grey bar in
 573 panel A corresponds to the period shown in Fig. 3.

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584 **Fig. 3. Carbon uptake enhancement extends beyond the regions of coral reefs.** The (A), mean
 585 ocean anthropogenic carbon uptake in 2081-2099 of RCP4.5 and the (B), coral reef-driven anomaly
 586 in ocean anthropogenic carbon uptake in 2081-2099 of RCP4.5₁₅₀. Stippling indicates the
 587 distribution of coral reefs.

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598 **Fig S1. Comparison of simulated ocean carbon uptake with observational products.** The (A),
 599 SeaFlux mean observational product of ocean total carbon flux in 2012-2021 (1), the (B),
 600 corresponding values in the NEMO-PISCES simulation of RCP4.5 (in the absence of the
 601 representation of coral reefs) and the (C), simulation anomalies relative to SeaFlux. Stippling
 602 indicates the distribution of coral reefs. (D), the globally integrated observed and simulated total
 603 carbon fluxes from 1990 to 2021. All fluxes are positive into the ocean.

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Fig. S2. The spatial distribution of ocean carbon uptake enhancement depends on emission scenario. The fraction of the (A), annual and (B), cumulative global enhancement in ocean anthropogenic carbon uptake that occurs in coral reef regions. The simulation legend is the same as in Figure 1. The first 4-8 years of each RCP are not shown due to the initially high sensitivity of relative anomalies.

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613 **Fig S3. The potential detectability of trends in induced alkalinity anomalies.** The simulated
 614 surface ocean trend in alkalinity due to coral reef carbonate production declines (ΔAlk ; mmol m^{-3}
 615 century^{-1}) in (A), RCP8.5₃₀₀ (B), RCP4.5₁₅₀ and (C), RCP2.6₃₀, with stippling indicating the
 616 distribution of coral reefs. Alkalinity trends are relative to the respective RCP standard simulations
 617 (RCP8.5, RCP.4.5 and RCP2.6) and computed locally using linear regressions applied across the
 618 duration of the simulations. Regressions in all surface ocean grid cells are significant at the $p <$
 619 0.05 level. Four coral reef time series stations of CO_2 system measurements (CHU: Chuuk Lagoon,
 620 KAN: Kaneohe Bay, CHE: Cheeca Rocks, LAP: La Parguera) are indicated on maps with (D), box
 621 and whisker plots of the alkalinity measurements at each station. Station alkalinity is recalculated
 622 with CO2SYS (2) using contemporaneous in situ $p\text{CO}_2$, pH, temperature and salinity
 623 measurements (3), and total dissolved inorganic phosphorus and total dissolved silicon
 624 concentrations taken from the nearest grid cell of the annual-mean World Ocean Atlas climatology
 625 (4). Purple box and whisker plots indicate the median (line), interquartile range (box), 5th
 626 percentiles (whiskers) and outliers (points). Green box and whisker plots indicate the mean (line),
 627 standard deviation (box), two times the standard deviation (whiskers) and outliers (points).

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630 **Fig S4. Declining coral reef carbonate production has limited influence on projections of**
 631 **ocean acidification.** The projected (A), global mean surface ocean pH for all simulations and (B),
 632 the anomalies in surface ocean pH in 2090-2110 of RCP4.5₁₅₀ relative to RCP4.5. Stippling
 633 indicates the distribution of coral reefs.

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